

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The mediating role of organizational commitment in the work-family conflict and turnover intention relationship

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Abstract

This research investigates the mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention among employees of PT. Hatten Bali Tbk. The study is motivated by the company's high turnover rate, which surpasses the normal threshold, and the growing challenge of balancing work and family responsibilities. Data were collected through interviews and structured questionnaires. A purposive sampling technique was employed to obtain 65 married employees as respondents. Data analysis was carried out using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method with SmartPLS 4.1 software. The empirical results demonstrate that work-family conflict has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention, while exerting a negative and significant impact on organizational commitment. In addition, organizational commitment shows a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. The findings further confirm that organizational commitment partially mediates the effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention. These results highlight the strategic importance of fostering organizational commitment as a mechanism to reduce the adverse consequences of work-family conflict and minimize employees' intention to leave. Theoretically, this study enriches the development of the Three-Component Model of organizational commitment, while practically offering valuable insights for human resource management in formulating effective retention strategies.

Keywords: Work-Family Conflict; Turnover Intention; Organizational Commitment; Human Resource Management

1. Introduction

Human resources (HR) are the most valuable assets of an organization, as a company's success depends not only on technology, capital, or business strategy but also on the quality and capability of its employees (Aji et al., 2024). Effective HR management is therefore essential for maintaining organizational competitiveness. One of the main challenges in HR management is turnover intention employees intention to leave their jobs which can negatively impact productivity, stability, and increase recruitment and training costs (Atmajaya et al., 2024). This issue has become increasingly complex in the modern workplace and requires serious attention from organizations. Understanding the factors that influence turnover intention is essential for organizations to develop effective retention strategies. One such factor is work-family conflict, which has a significant impact on employee productivity, well-being, and stress levels (Junianingrum & Mas'ud, 2021). Work-family conflict consists of two main forms: work-to-family conflict, where work interferes with family life, and family-to-work conflict, where family responsibilities hinder job performance (Divayani & Darmawan, 2024).

The negative impact of work-family conflict on turnover intention is not always direct, as organizational commitment serves as a mediating variable (Sofyan & Iqbal, 2024). Employees with high commitment levels tend to remain in their jobs despite experiencing conflicts between work and personal life (Hermawati et al., 2022). Organizational commitment reflects an employee's emotional, economic, and moral attachment to the organization (Hamdani &

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Muzahid, 2023). Several studies also indicate that work-family conflict negatively affects organizational commitment, as difficulties in balancing family and work roles can reduce employees' loyalty to the organization (Ashary et al., 2021; Radityan et al., 2024; Sanipah et al., 2024).

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Influence of Work-family Conflict on Turnover Intention

Work-family conflict (WFC) occurs when job and family demands are imbalanced, creating emotional pressure that can increase employees' intention to leave their jobs. Various studies have shown that WFC has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Delvina et al., (2024) and Pramudya et al., (2025) found that work-family conflict encourages employees to seek jobs that offer better work-life balance. Similarly, Razaki & Rozana, (2022) and Rihayana et al., (2025) stated that the higher the level of work-family conflict, the greater the employees' intention to quit. Yildiz et al., (2021) also confirmed that WFC consistently increases turnover intention across various sectors and work cultures.

H1: Work-family conflict has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention.

2.2. The Influence of Work-family Conflict on Organizational commitment

Previous studies have shown that work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment. Ashary et al., (2021) and Hernita, (2020) found that increasing conflict between work and family reduces employee loyalty and attachment to the organization. Radityan et al., (2024) and Sanipah et al., (2024) also demonstrated that such conflict decreases employee engagement and motivation to remain with the organization in the long term. Furthermore, Srinofita et al., (2022) revealed that work-family conflict lowers all dimensions of organizational commitment including affective, continuance, and normative commitment, thus increasing the likelihood that employees will seek other job opportunities.

H2: Work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment.

2.3. The Influence of Organizational commitment on Turnover Intention

Organizational commitment is an important factor that influences employee loyalty to the organization, reflecting emotional, normative, and continuance attachment to the workplace. Studies have shown that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Diputra et al., (2021) and Jaya & Widiastini, (2021) found that employees with high commitment tend to stay, while those with low commitment are more likely to leave. Kalsum et al., (2022) and Rahmizal & Lasmi, (2021) also confirmed that strong loyalty and affective commitment reduce employees' intention to quit. Furthermore, Rizki & Juhaeti, (2022) emphasized that organizational commitment not only decreases turnover intention but also enhances workforce stability.

H3: Organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

2.4. Organizational commitment Mediates the Influence of Work-family Conflict on Turnover Intention

Previous studies have shown that organizational commitment mediates the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention. Finthariasari et al., (2020) and Hamdani & Muzahid, (2023) found that an increase in work-family conflict reduces organizational commitment, which in turn raises employees' intention to leave. Hermawati et al., (2022) and Li et al., (2021) emphasized that when work interferes with family life, employees experience a decline in emotional attachment to the organization, increasing the likelihood of turnover. Zhou et al., (2020) further noted that enhancing organizational commitment through supportive work-life balance initiatives can mitigate the negative impact of work-family conflict on turnover intention.

H4: Organizational commitment mediates the effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention.

3. Methodology

This study employs a quantitative approach with a causal associative research design aimed at examining cause-and-effect relationships among variables. The research was conducted at PT. Hatten Bali Tbk, located at Jl. Bypass Ngurah Rai No. 393, Sanur Kauh, South Denpasar, Denpasar City, Bali 80227. The Turnover Intention variable (Y) consists of three indicators: thoughts of quitting, intention to quit, and intention to search for another job. The Work-Family

Conflict variable (X) is measured using three indicators: time-based conflict, strain-based conflict, and behavior-based conflict. The Organizational Commitment variable (Z) serves as the mediating variable and includes three indicators: affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment.

The study population includes all 108 employees of PT. Hatten Bali Tbk. The sample was determined using purposive sampling based on the criterion of employees who are married, resulting in a total sample of 65 respondents. Data were collected through interviews and surveys using a Likert scale questionnaire ranging from 1 to 5, with response options: strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). The research instruments were tested for validity and reliability. Data analysis was carried out using SEM-PLS (Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling) with the help of SmartPLS 4.1 software.

4. Research Result

To describe the respondents' assessments of each research instrument, the responses were grouped into five (5) rating scale categories. The formation of these categories was based on interval calculation, which was done by subtracting the lowest value from the highest value and then dividing the result by the number of scales used (5-1), resulting in an interval value of 0.80. The assessment criteria used can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Measurement Criteria

Average Score	Category		
	Turnover Intention	Work-Family Conflict	Organizational Commitment
1,00 - 1,80	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
1,81 - 2,60	Low	Low	Low
2,61 - 3,40	Moderate High	Moderate High	Moderate High
3,41 - 4,20	High	High	High
4,21 - 5,00	Very High	Very High	Very High

4.1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

4.1.1. Turnover Intention

The turnover intention variable (Y) is an endogenous variable measured using 16 statements on a 5-point Likert Scale. Based on respondents' answers, the proportion of responses indicates that the level of employee turnover intention falls within the high moderate category as shown at Table 1.

Table 2 Description of Respondents' Responses to Turnover Intention

Statement		Distribution of respondent's answer (person)					Total responses	Mean	Category
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	I would consider changing jobs if there were a better opportunity.	3	7	21	11	23	239	3.68	High
2	I have started to feel like leaving this job.	1	15	25	17	7	209	3.22	Moderate High
3	I feel less enthusiastic or bored with my current job.	3	20	22	12	8	197	3.03	Moderate High
4	My current job does not match the skills that I possess.	3	21	16	16	9	202	3.11	Moderate High
5	I feel that my work is excessive or beyond my responsibilities.	3	10	24	15	13	220	3.38	Moderate High

6	My work environment feels uncomfortable or unsupportive.	1	18	23	12	11	209	3.22	Moderate High
Thoughts of Quitting								3.32	Moderate High
7	I am looking for job opportunities elsewhere.	2	14	26	14	9	209	3.22	Moderate High
8	I often think about quitting this job.	3	13	21	10	18	222	3.42	High
9	I have contacted friends or acquaintances to look for job vacancies.	3	13	28	12	9	206	3.17	Moderate High
10	I actively search for job vacancy information.	6	12	23	14	10	205	3.15	Moderate High
11	I have written or sent a job application letter.	6	14	32	6	7	189	2.91	Moderate High
12	I regularly apply for jobs at other companies.	7	14	34	6	4	181	2.78	Moderate High
Intention to Quit								3.11	Moderate High
13	I am interested in job offers from other companies.	4	12	22	11	16	218	3.35	Moderate High
14	I want to find a job that offers better income or benefits.	2	5	21	13	24	247	3.80	High
15	I am looking for a job that provides better security or stability.	2	10	20	15	18	232	3.57	High
16	I feel that there are no career development opportunities in my current workplace.	4	8	23	12	18	227	3.49	High
Intention to Search for Another Job								3.55	High
Overall Average of Turnover intention								3.28	Moderate High

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 2, respondent's perceptions of the turnover intention variable show an overall mean score of 3.28, which falls under the fairly high category. This indicates that employees at PT. Hatten Bali Tbk have a relatively high level of intention to leave their jobs. The statement with the lowest score is "I regularly apply for jobs at other companies," with a mean of 2.78, suggesting that employees are not yet actively applying for other jobs. Conversely, the statement with the highest score is "I want to find a job that offers better income or benefits," with a mean of 3.80, indicating that most employees are motivated to seek better employment opportunities offering higher compensation or improved facilities.

4.2. Work-family Conflict

The work-family conflict variable in this study is an exogenous variable, symbolized as X, and measured using 16 statement items assessed on a 5-point Likert scale. Based on the respondents' answers, the distribution of responses regarding the work-family conflict variable can be summarized as follows.

Table 3 Description of Respondents' Responses to Work-family Conflict

Statement		Distribution of respondent's answer (person)					Total responses	Mean	Category
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	I feel that my time for family has decreased because of work.	9	8	17	10	21	221	3.40	Moderate High
2	I often cannot participate in family activities because of work.	5	13	18	12	17	218	3.35	Moderate High
3	I rarely have time to socialize outside of work.	9	9	20	7	20	215	3.31	Moderate High
4	I do not have enough time to help with household chores.	9	10	16	15	15	212	3.26	Moderate High
5	I often continue to work during holidays.	1	11	20	14	19	234	3.60	High
6	My irregular working hours make it difficult to manage time with my family.	9	11	14	12	19	216	3.32	Moderate High
Time-Based Conflict								3.37	Moderate High
7	Family problems often interfere with my work.	9	12	13	21	10	206	3.17	Moderate High
8	When there are problems at home. I find it difficult to focus on work.	9	9	16	10	21	220	3.38	Moderate High
9	Family problems make me less productive.	9	10	15	14	17	215	3.31	Moderate High
10	Household responsibilities make it difficult for me to concentrate at work.	9	10	17	10	19	215	3.31	High
11	The heavy workload makes me feel tired at home.	1	13	17	7	27	241	3.71	High
12	I feel that I pay less attention to my family because of my job.	2	13	21	10	19	226	3.48	High
Strain-Based Conflict								3.39	Moderate High
13	My family has complained because I am too busy with work.	2	15	15	13	20	229	3.52	High
14	I feel that I do not get enough support from my family regarding my job.	10	15	21	15	4	183	2.82	Moderate High
15	I feel too tired to do activities at home after work.	1	11	21	5	27	241	3.71	High
16	I often miss family moments because of work-related matters.	9	8	18	10	20	219	3.37	Moderate High
Behavior-Based Conflict								3.35	Moderate High
Overall Average of Work-family conflict								3.38	Moderate High

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 3, respondents perceptions of the work-family conflict variable show an overall mean score of 3.38, which falls into the fairly high category. This indicates that employees of PT. Hatten Bali Tbk experience a relatively high level of work-family conflict. The lowest-rated statement is "I feel that I do not get enough support from my family regarding my job.," with a mean score of 2.82, suggesting that employees somewhat feel a lack of family support related to their jobs. Meanwhile, the highest-rated statements are "High workload makes me feel tired at home" and "I feel too tired to do activities at home after work.," both with a mean score of 3.71, indicating that employees often experience fatigue after work due to heavy workloads.

4.3. Organizational Commitment

Table 4 Description of Respondents' Responses to Organizational Commitment

Statement		Distribution of respondent's answer (person)					Total responses	Mean	Category
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	I feel that I am an important part of this company.	12	15	10	10	18	202	3.11	Moderate High
2	I feel proud to work at this company.	1	19	12	10	23	230	3.54	High
3	I have an emotional attachment to my workplace.	12	16	15	10	12	189	2.91	Moderate High
4	I feel that every problem faced by the company is also my responsibility.	9	19	12	13	12	195	3.00	Moderate High
Affective Commitment								3.14	Moderate High
5	I want to continue working at this company because I feel that my life needs are fulfilled here.	0	17	17	13	18	227	3.49	High
6	I continue to work at this company not merely for the benefits. but because of the comfort I feel.	12	16	10	10	17	199	3.06	Moderate High
Continuance Commitment								3.28	Moderate High
7	I feel that being part of this company is a form of my moral responsibility.	0	21	14	6	24	228	3.51	High
8	I believe that my work in this company provides real benefits for me as an employee.	2	9	22	7	25	239	3.68	High
9	I feel that the company's facilities greatly assist me in carrying out my duties.	0	17	16	13	19	229	3.52	High
10	I am confident that this company offers good opportunities for my career development in the future.	5	14	27	12	7	197	3.03	Moderate High
Normative Commitment								3.43	Moderate High
Overall Average of organizational commitment								3.28	Moderate High

Source: Primary data, 2025

The organizational commitment variable in this study serves as a mediating variable, symbolized as Z, and is measured using 10 statement items assessed on a 5-point Likert scale. Based on the respondents' answers, the distribution of responses regarding the organizational commitment variable can be summarized as follows.

Based on Table 4, the respondents' perception of the organizational commitment variable shows an overall mean score of 3.28, which falls under the fairly high category. This indicates that employees of PT. Hatten Bali Tbk generally demonstrate a moderate level of organizational commitment. The lowest-rated statement was "I have an emotional attachment to my workplace," with a mean score of 2.91, suggesting that employees have not yet fully developed a strong emotional connection to their organization. Conversely, the highest-rated statement was "I believe that my job in this company provides real benefits for me as an employee," with a mean score of 3.68, indicating that employees feel their work at PT. Hatten Bali Tbk brings meaningful personal benefits.

4.4. Outer Model Test Result

The outer model or measurement model in Partial Least Square (PLS)-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is used to assess the validity and reliability of indicators forming latent variables. In this study, all variables are latent with reflective indicators, and the outer model evaluation focuses on several aspects. Convergent validity is tested to determine the validity of each indicator forming a variable, where an indicator is considered valid if it has an outer loading value above 0.70 and a t-statistic greater than 1.96. The results of the outer loading analysis are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Results of Outer Loadings Testing

Statement-variable	Outer Loadings	T Statistics	Explanation
Y _{1.1} <- Turnover intention	0.863	24.876	Valid
Y _{1.2} <- Turnover intention	0.852	27.707	Valid
Y _{1.3} <- Turnover intention	0.841	35.390	Valid
Y _{1.4} <- Turnover intention	0.870	22.897	Valid
Y _{1.5} <- Turnover intention	0.886	35.259	Valid
Y _{1.6} <- Turnover intention	0.829	22.665	Valid
Y _{2.1} <- Turnover intention	0.862	28.776	Valid
Y _{2.2} <- Turnover intention	0.922	52.594	Valid
Y _{2.3} <- Turnover intention	0.775	15.297	Valid
Y _{2.4} <- Turnover intention	0.854	26.600	Valid
Y _{2.5} <- Turnover intention	0.750	17.538	Valid
Y _{2.6} <- Turnover intention	0.721	15.103	Valid
Y _{3.1} <- Turnover intention	0.926	53.344	Valid
Y _{3.2} <- Turnover intention	0.885	42.412	Valid
Y _{3.3} <- Turnover intention	0.884	35.080	Valid
Y _{3.4} <- Turnover intention	0.813	10.944	Valid
X _{1.1} <- Work-family conflict	0.961	112.148	Valid
X _{1.2} <- Work-family conflict	0.910	39.518	Valid
X _{1.3} <- Work-family conflict	0.941	69.990	Valid
X _{1.4} <- Work-family conflict	0.951	88.675	Valid
X _{1.5} <- Work-family conflict	0.872	24.158	Valid
X _{1.6} <- Work-family conflict	0.938	65.925	Valid

X2.1<- Work-family conflict	0.920	43.852	Valid
X2.2<- Work-family conflict	0.952	84.707	Valid
X2.3<- Work-family conflict	0.940	70.305	Valid
X2.4<- Work-family conflict	0.933	64.671	Valid
X2.5<- Work-family conflict	0.923	68.263	Valid
X2.6<- Work-family conflict	0.895	39.447	Valid
X3.1<- Work-family conflict	0.937	83.856	Valid
X3.2<- Work-family conflict	0.856	26.839	Valid
X3.3<- Work-family conflict	0.903	42.721	Valid
X3.4<- Work-family conflict	0.940	62.417	Valid
Z1.1<- Organizational commitment	0.969	105.216	Valid
Z1.2<- Organizational commitment	0.965	140.647	Valid
Z1.3<- Organizational commitment	0.930	45.841	Valid
Z1.4<- Organizational commitment	0.929	46.953	Valid
Z2.1<- Organizational commitment	0.941	64.290	Valid
Z2.2<- Organizational commitment	0.961	74.214	Valid
Z3.1<- Organizational commitment	0.953	92.054	Valid
Z3.2<- Organizational commitment	0.919	67.832	Valid
Z3.3<- Organizational commitment	0.937	67.653	Valid
Z3.4<- Organizational commitment	0.787	20.806	Valid

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 5, the convergent validity results show that all indicators for the three variables turnover intention (16 items), work-family conflict (16 items), and organizational commitment (10 items) have outer loading values above 0.70. This indicates that every statement used effectively reflects and measures its respective latent variable.

Discriminant validity assesses the extent to which a construct differs from other constructs. It is evaluated using cross-loading values, where an indicator is considered valid if its loading on its associated variable is higher than its loading on other variables. The results of the cross-loading test are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 Results of Cross Loading

Statement Item	Variable		
	Turnover intention	Work-family conflict	Organizational commitment
Y1.1	0.863	0.679	-0.662
Y1.2	0.852	0.700	-0.619
Y1.3	0.841	0.732	-0.665
Y1.4	0.870	0.782	-0.672
Y1.5	0.886	0.719	-0.677
Y1.6	0.829	0.724	-0.642
Y2.1	0.862	0.701	-0.559

Y _{2.2}	0.922	0.760	-0.721
Y _{2.3}	0.775	0.681	-0.543
Y _{2.4}	0.854	0.700	-0.593
Y _{2.5}	0.750	0.624	-0.456
Y _{2.6}	0.721	0.577	-0.488
Y _{3.1}	0.926	0.775	-0.672
Y _{3.2}	0.885	0.746	-0.678
Y _{3.3}	0.884	0.738	-0.708
Y _{3.4}	0.813	0.600	-0.698
X _{1.1}	0.766	0.961	-0.665
X _{1.2}	0.756	0.910	-0.641
X _{1.3}	0.751	0.941	-0.647
X _{1.4}	0.770	0.951	-0.661
X _{1.5}	0.699	0.872	-0.552
X _{1.6}	0.765	0.938	-0.611
X _{2.1}	0.743	0.920	-0.651
X _{2.2}	0.789	0.952	-0.622
X _{2.3}	0.791	0.940	-0.652
X _{2.4}	0.757	0.933	-0.611
X _{2.5}	0.793	0.923	-0.639
X _{2.6}	0.776	0.895	-0.589
X _{3.1}	0.804	0.937	-0.631
X _{3.2}	0.741	0.856	-0.601
X _{3.3}	0.808	0.903	-0.613
X _{3.4}	0.770	0.940	-0.617
Z _{1.1}	-0.710	-0.645	0.969
Z _{1.2}	-0.717	-0.652	0.965
Z _{1.3}	-0.682	-0.636	0.930
Z _{1.4}	-0.644	-0.602	0.929
Z _{2.1}	-0.759	-0.673	0.941
Z _{2.2}	-0.736	-0.650	0.961
Z _{3.1}	-0.676	-0.608	0.953
Z _{3.2}	-0.662	-0.589	0.919
Z _{3.3}	-0.696	-0.667	0.937
Z _{3.4}	-0.644	-0.568	0.787

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 6, the cross-loading values show that each indicator correlates more strongly with its respective variable turnover intention (Y), work-family conflict (X), and organizational commitment (Z) than with other variables, indicating that all items are valid. Another method to assess discriminant validity is by comparing the Average Variance

Extracted (AVE) values with the correlations between constructs. The model is considered to have adequate discriminant validity if the AVE value exceeds 0.50. The AVE test results are presented in Table 7 .

Table 7 Results of Average Variance Extracted

Variabel Penelitian	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Turnover intention (Y)	0.718
Work-family conflict (X)	0.853
Organizational commitment (Z)	0.866

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 7 , the AVE values for the variables turnover intention, work-family conflict, and organizational commitment are 0.718, 0.853, and 0.866, respectively. Since all AVE values are greater than 0.50, the model can be considered adequate and demonstrates good discriminant validity.

Composite reliability is an outer model test used to assess the reliability of a block of indicators forming a construct. A set of indicators measuring a variable is considered to have good composite reliability if the composite reliability value exceeds 0.70. A variable is also considered reliable if its Cronbach's alpha (α) value is above 0.70. The results of the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha tests are presented in Table 8.

Table 8 Results of Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbachs Alpha	Explanation
Turnover intention (Y)	0.976	0.973	Reliable
Work-family conflict (X)	0.989	0.988	Reliable
Organizational commitment (Z)	0.985	0.982	Reliable

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on the results of the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha tests in Table 8, the values for turnover intention, work-family conflict, and organizational commitment are all above 0.70. This indicates that these variables have good reliability.

4.5. Inner Model Test Results

4.5.1. R-Square

R-Square (R^2) indicates the strength of the effect that variations in independent variables have on the dependent variable. A R-Square value greater than 0.50 is categorized as a strong model. The R-Square values are presented in Table 9.

Table 9 Results of R-square

Variabel	R Square
Organizational commitment	0.459
Turnover intention	0.753

Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 9, the R-square value for organizational commitment is 0.459, indicating that 45.9% of the variation in organizational commitment can be explained by work-family conflict, while the remaining 54.1% is influenced by other factors outside the model. For turnover intention, the R-square value is 0.753, meaning that 75.3% of its variation can be explained by work-family conflict and organizational commitment, with the remaining 24.7% accounted for by variables outside the model.

4.5.2. Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) measures how well the observed values are predicted by the model and its parameters. A Q² value greater than 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance, whereas a Q² value less than 0 indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. The classification of Q² values is as follows: Q² > 0.35 indicates a strong model, Q² between 0.15 and 0.35 indicates a moderate model, and Q² < 0.02 indicates a weak model. The calculation of Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) is presented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R1^2) (1 - R2^2) \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0,459) (1 - 0,753) \\
 &= 1 - (0,541) (0,247) \\
 &= 1 - 0,134 = 0,866
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the calculation, the Q² value is 0.866, which is close to 1. According to the criteria for model strength based on Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²), this indicates a strong model. The predictive relevance value of 0.866 means that 86.6% of the variation in turnover intention can be explained, directly or indirectly, by work-family conflict and organizational commitment within the research model, while the remaining 13.4% is explained by variables outside the model.

4.5.3. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using SmartPLS 4.1 software with the probability (p-values) approach. If the obtained p-value < 0.05 (α = 5%) or the t-statistic > 1.96, it indicates a significant relationship between the latent variables, namely work-family conflict, organizational commitment, and turnover intention. The results of the hypothesis testing in this study are presented in Table 10.

Figure 1 Mediation Model

Table 10 Results of Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Original Sampel	t statistic	p values	Explanation
Direct Influence				
Work-family conflict -> Turnover intention	0.603	6.606	0.000	Significant
Work-family conflict -> Organizational commitment	-0.678	9.987	0.000	Significant
Organizational commitment -> Turnover intention	-0.338	3.534	0.001	Significant
Indirect Influence				

Work-family conflict -> Organizational commitment -> Turnover intention	0.229	3.326	0.001	Significant
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Source: Primary data, 2025

Based on Table 10, the original sample value for the effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention is known to be 0.603, with p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ and t-statistics of $6.606 > 1.96$, indicating that work-family conflict has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. This result means that if work-family conflict increases, it will have a tangible impact on the increase in turnover intention. Thus, the first hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Based on Table 10, the original sample value for the effect of work-family conflict on organizational commitment is known to be -0.678, with p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ and t-statistics of $9.987 > 1.96$, indicating that work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment. This result means that if work-family conflict increases, it will have a tangible impact on the decrease in organizational commitment. Thus, the second hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Based on Table 10, the original sample value for the effect of organizational commitment on turnover intention is known to be -0.338, with p-values of $0.001 < 0.05$ and t-statistics of $3.534 > 1.96$, indicating that organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. This result means that if organizational commitment increases, it will have a tangible impact on the decrease in turnover intention. Thus, the third hypothesis in this study is accepted.

Based on Table 10, the results of the indirect effect analysis show that the p-values are $0.001 < 0.05$ and the t-statistics are $3.326 > 1.96$, with an original sample value of 0.229, which means the organizational commitment variable can mediate the effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention. Furthermore, the direct effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention has p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ and t-statistics of $6.606 > 1.96$, and an original sample value of 0.603. Based on the criteria for the mediation test, this indicates that organizational commitment partially (complementary) mediates the effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention. Thus, the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted.

The total effect is the sum of the direct effect (c) and the indirect effect ($a \times b$). Table 10 shows that the direct effect of work-family conflict on turnover intention is 0.603, while the indirect effect of work-family conflict through organizational commitment on turnover intention is 0.229. Therefore, the total effect of all existing influences is $0.603 + 0.229 = 0.832$, which indicates that the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention, both directly and through organizational commitment, is very strong.

5. Conclusions

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that work-family conflict has a positive and significant effect on the turnover intention of employees at PT. Hatten Bali Tbk., meaning the higher the conflict felt by employees, the greater their tendency to leave the company. Furthermore, work-family conflict was proven to have a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment, which means that an increase in conflict will reduce employee attachment to the company. Moreover, organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention, indicating that the lower the employee commitment, the higher the desire to quit. Other results confirm that organizational commitment is capable of partially mediating the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention. Thus, work-family conflict not only has a direct impact on turnover intention but also an indirect impact through the decrease in organizational commitment.

Recommendations

The company is advised to pay attention to the work-family conflict experienced by employees, especially regarding the high workload which has the potential to cause physical and mental fatigue. Policies such as adjusting working hours or implementing a more flexible shift system can help employees balance their work and family roles, thereby increasing their attachment to the organization. Additionally, the company needs to strengthen organizational commitment, particularly the emotional attachment dimension, by providing greater support for employees' family needs. This step will foster a feeling that the company cares, making employees more loyal and committed.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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